

On Munjisthin. Part II.*

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On oxidation with an alkaline solution of potassium permanganate, 2-*p*-toluoylbenzoic acid (Friedel and Crafts, *Ann. Chim. Phys.* 1888, vi, 14, 446) gives benzophenone-2:4'-dicarboxylic acid (Lamprecht, *Ber.*, 1895, 28, 1184) which on treatment with sulphuric acid gives anthraquinone- β -carboxylic acid; it appeared to us to be of interest to enquire, whether a similar reaction could not be applied for the synthesis of 2:4-dihydroxy-3-carboxyanthraquinone, which represents, most probably, the constitution of munjisthin.

We condensed 2:4-dimethoxytoluene with phthalic anhydride in presence of aluminium chloride and obtained in this manner 2-(2':4'-dimethoxy-3'-methyl)-benzoylbenzoic acid. The substance, however, resisted all attempts at oxidation.

Subsequently, the benzoylbenzoic acid was converted into the corresponding anthraquinone, by treatment with sulphuric acid and from this, by de-methylation, rubiadin was obtained. Attempts at direct oxidation of rubiadin have also, so far, failed.

EXPERIMENTAL.

2-Methoxy-6-nitrotoluene.—Starting from 2:6-dinitrotoluene, we prepared 2-amino-6-nitrotoluene (Cunerth, *Annalen*, 1874, 173, 221; Ullmann, *Ber.*, 1884, 17, 1958) and from this by diazotisation, 2-oxo-6-nitrotoluene (Ullmann, *loc. cit.*) which, on methylation, gave 2-methoxy-6-nitrotoluene, identical with one of the products obtained by Simonsen and Nayak (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 828) by the nitration of 8-acetylamino-2-methoxytoluene followed by deacetylation and removal of amino-group.

2-Methoxy-6-aminotoluene Hydrochloride.—2-Methoxy-6-nitrotoluene is reduced with tin and hydrochloric acid, the tin separated by means of sulphuretted hydrogen and the filtrate evaporated to

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dryness. It forms needles from alcohol, m.p. 234-35°. (Found: N, 8.28. Calc. N, 8.07 per cent.).

2-Methoxy-6-hydroxytoluene.—The amine hydrochloride (2.5 g.) is added to boiling dilute sulphuric acid (17 g. conc. acid in 175 c.c. water), kept for a few minutes at this temperature and rapidly cooled with stirring. When the temperature reaches 5°, 2*N*-sodium nitrite solution (9 c.c.) is gradually added and the mixture stirred for two hours. Further 17g. of sulphuric acid (in 175 c.c. of water) are now added and the mixture warmed on the water-bath at 40-45° for about two hours. The mixture is then cooled, extracted with ether, the ethereal solution dried by means of anhydrous sodium sulphate, and the ether distilled off. The residue has b.p. 242-44°. (Found: C, 69.72; H, 7.30. $C_8H_{10}O_2$ requires C, 69.56; H, 7.25 per cent.).

2:6-Dimethoxytoluene.—The hydroxymethoxytoluene is methylated in the usual manner. The dimethoxy compound distilled at 220-22°. The distillate solidified in the receiver and crystallised as colourless plates from alcohol, m.p. 35°. (Found: C, 70.84; H, 7.71. $C_9H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 71.05; H, 7.89 per cent.).

2-(2':4'-Dimethoxy-3'-methyl)-benzoylbenzoic Acid.—2:6-Dimethoxytoluene (5.5 g.) and phthalic anhydride (5 g.) are covered with carbon bisulphide (100 c.c.) Finely powdered aluminium chloride (10 g.) is gradually added and the flask heated on the water-bath under reflux for about 10 hours. Carbon bisulphide is then decanted off, ice and hydrochloric acid are added and steam passed through the mixture. The residue is filtered, washed, extracted with sodium carbonate solution and filtered. The filtrate, on acidification, gave a white precipitate which crystallised as plates from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 180°. (Found: C, 67.81; H, 5.05. $C_{17}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 68.00; H, 5.83 per cent.).

*Rubiadin Methyl Ether**.—The benzoylbenzoic acid (5 g.) was mixed with sulphuric acid (10 g. *d* 1.84) and fuming sulphuric acid (50 g., 20 per cent. SO_3) and heated on the water-bath for four hours. It was then poured on ice, filtered and the residue extracted successively with boiling water, boiling dilute sodium carbonate solution and cold 2 per cent. caustic soda solution. The residue is washed with water and dried. It crystallised as needles from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 188-189°. (Found: C, 72.06; H, 4.74. $C_{16}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 71.64; H, 4.5 per cent.).

* The substance appears to be identical with the 8-*O*-methylrubiadin, m.p. 186°, of Jones and Robertson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, p. 1704).—*Editor*.

Rubiadin.—Methoxyrubiadin (5 g.) was thoroughly mixed with powdered aluminium chloride (3 g.). The temperature of the mixture was slowly raised to 200° in course of an hour and the mixture kept at this temperature for another hour. The mass is then poured into ice-water, boiled and filtered. The residue is treated with dilute caustic soda solution, filtered, and the filtrate acidified, boiled and filtered. The residue was crystallised from a large volume of glacial acetic acid; m.p. 290-291°. (Found: C, 70·69; H, 4·01. $C_{15}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 70·87; H, 3·93 per cent.).

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